

A SCRUTINY ON THE SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE LEVELS AND PURPOSES OF THE STUDENTS STUDYING IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL TRAINING AND SPORTS SCIENCES

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Abstract:

The study has been conducted in order to determine the social media utilization levels and objectives of the students studying in the field of Physical Education and Sports Sciences. The study has been conducted in scanning model. The population of the study consisted on students studying at Mehmet Akif Ersoy University, Physical Education and Sports School of Higher Education, Physical Education and Sports Teacher Training School, and Sports Management and Coaching departments. The sample group consisted of 442 individuals determined through random-selection method among those students. The data was obtained by means of a survey method in the study. Understandability, and scope validity and reliability of the survey developed were ensured. The survey's Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient was found as 0,81. The surveys were conducted through the random sampling method in the sampling group by means of one-to-one discussions. Totally 442 individuals responded to the survey, 138 of whom being female and 304 male. As a statistical operation form, the data obtained, frequency (%), Chi-Square, Independent- Samples T, and Kruskal Wallis H tests were applied. In the determination of the differences, 0,05 significance level was accepted and the comments were made according to the distributions and averages of the responses given to each question. It was determined according to the data obtained that the participants reach social media in general by means of the internet connections of their mobile phones; that they provide their social network connections by Instagram, Whatsapp, and Facebook; that their period of utilization is between 2-hour and 4-hour intervals on a daily basis; and that there are statistically significant differences between the variables of gender and department of study in view of their type, period, and objectives of social media utilization at a 0,05 significance level ($P < 0,05$). It appears that females use social media more than the males and that the teacher training department uses it more than the other departments. As a result, the participants use social media in different ways and periods in general and that their

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purposes of use are to get to know and meet new friends, write in the contents of social media, and shop.

Keywords: social media, utilization, objective, sports sciences, student

1. Introduction

The rapid development of technology and the internet's access to almost all levels of our lives and its widespread use among people are affecting the lives of persons in multiple aspects and change them. The internet and the amenities it provides enable people to enter into a fast and effective communication process, learn the incidents and news in the world in a short period, improve themselves in their working fields, keep track of their areas of interests, and share their own experiences and opinions.

Social media are considered an important element of the internet in this regard and they alter the manner of establishing communication and sharing information of the people, to a significant extent. Social media present opportunities for the people to reflect themselves, constitute communities, and create cooperation and sharing environments (Murray, 2008). While social media have different definitions in the written literatures, Laird (2014) underlines that social media have a structure that aims to establish a community and that provides preoccupation with the information and content sharing and exchange of opinions, as well as comments, and personal messages. Rao and Shalini (2013) define social media as the internet and mobile services that ensure the dissemination of the contents developed by the user or the participation in the online communities and the state that the services like the blogs, social network sites, and media sharing are included in those services.

With its simplest definition, social media are the environments of communication where the web 2.0 technologies are used (Gunelius, 2011, s. 10). Social media are new type of media used by people in order to socialize, which are different from the conventional media (Lietsala and Sirkkunan, 2008, s. 18). They are related with the sharing of information, experience, and viewpoints on the community-based websites. The state of the web 2.0 that is dynamic, that provides users with the possibility of creating content, and that is social based has a significant role in the emergence of social media (Bozarth, 2010, s. 11; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010, s. 60).

Through this type of communication referred to as social media, individuals are not subject to being informed unilaterally as opposed to the customary application, but, at the same time, they take place in a process of interaction and impact concurrently via the internet (Alav, 2014, s. 3).

The internet, which was commenced to be used in Turkey in 1994, has started to be utilized in every section of the society, particularly the public institutions and organizations, in a widespread manner as of 2017. In the recent years, the rapid developments in the computer technology have brought along the popularization of smart telephones and presence of the social media on the world's agenda in an efficient manner, whereby paving the way for it to be one of the indispensable communication

resources of the world. This way, the social media entered the living areas of individuals in almost entire world and those of societies, and became efficient.

This study has been performed in order to determine the frequency of using social media, which have been effectively used for different purposes among individuals in the recent years, by the students studying in the field of sports sciences, as well as their social media accounts, usage levels, objectives, and thoughts.

2. Material and Method

This study has been performed in order to determine the social media usage levels of the students studying in the field of Study Physical Education and Sports Sciences, and their reasons.

The study is a study performed in the screening model. The screening model, is a study approach that aims to describe a situation that exists presently or that has existed in the past. It tries to describe the incident, individual, or object that is the subject matter of the study, within its own conditions and as is. No effort is used to change or affect them in any manner (Karasar, 2007).

The population of the study is the 950 students studying at Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Physical Education and Sports School of Higher Education, the departments of Physical Education and Sports teacher training, Sports management, and Coaching education. The sampling group consists of the 442 students chosen through the random sampling method among the aforesaid students.

In the study, the data was acquired through a questionnaire method. The reliability, understandability and content validity of the questionnaire developed were ensured. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient of the questionnaire was found as 0,81. Numerous methods are available for calculating the reliability of the questionnaires developed for a study. The mostly used one of them is the Alfa Model (Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient) (Lorlu, 2015). Cronbach's Alpha number is a value between 0 and 1; it is the mean value of the weighed standard change found by proportioning the sum of the variances of the "k" number of articles in the scales to the general variance (Özdamar, 2002). Alpha coefficient is a benchmark of the internal coherence of the articles of a questionnaire. In Questionnaires were applied to the sampling group through the random sampling method through one-on-one interviews. Questionnaire was filled in by 138 female and 304 males, totaling to 442 individuals.

As the statistical transaction, frequency (%), Chi-Square, Independent- Samples T, Kruskal Wallis H, tests were used on the data obtained. In the determination of the differences, between the variables, 0,05 was accepted as the significance range and comments were also made according to the distributions of the answers given to each question and their averages.

3. Findings

Table 1: The Distribution of the Participants' Individual Properties

Variables		N. Distribution	%. Distribution
Gender	Female	138	31, 2
	Male	304	68, 8
	Total	442	100, 0

Age distribution		N. Distribution	%. Distribution
	19-20	130	29, 4
	21-22	164	37, 1
	23 and above	148	33, 5
	Total	442	100, 0
The department where they study	Physical Education and Sports teacher training	118	26, 7
	Coaching education	136	30, 8
	Sports management	188	42, 5
	Total	442	100, 0

Table 2: The Distribution of the State of the Participants for having an Internet Network

Variables		N. Distribution	%.Distribution
Home internet	Yes	308	69, 7
	No	134	30, 3
	Total	442	100, 0
Phone internet	Yes	404	91, 4
	No	38	8, 6
	Total	442	100, 0

Table 3: The Distribution of the Communication Tools, Programs, and Usage Periods used by the Participants and the State of the Internet for being Sufficient

Variables		N. Distribution	% Distribution
Communication tool	Cell telephone	394	89, 1
	Tablet	14	3, 2
	Computer	34	7, 7
	Total	442	100, 0
Social account	Facebook	64	14, 5
	Twitter	20	4, 5
	Instagram	216	48, 9
	Snapchat	20	4, 5
	WhatsApp	120	27, 1
	Others	2	, 5
	Total	442	100, 0
Daily periods of use	1 hours	54	12, 2
	2 hours	112	25, 3
	3 hours	90	20, 4
	4 hours and above	186	42, 1

	Total	442	100,0
Internet sufficiency condition	Yes	252	57,0
	No	190	43,0
	Total	442	100,0

3.1 The Participants' Comparative Statistical Analysis Distributions as per the Gender and Department Variables

Table 4: The Distribution of the Communication Tools used by the Participants as per the Gender Variable

Variables	Cell telephone	Tablet	Computer	Total
Female	120	8	10	138
	87,0%	5,8%	7,2%	100,0%
Male	274	6	24	304
	90,1%	2,0%	7,9%	100,0%
Total	394	14	34	442
	89,1%	3,2%	7,7%	100,0%

$\chi^2 = 4,540$ $P = 0,103$

Table 5: The Distribution of the Social Account Network used by the Participants as per the Gender Variable

Variables	Facebook	Twitter	Instagram	Snapchat	WhatsApp	Other	Total
Female	12	4	58	8	56	0	138
	8,7%	2,9%	42,0%	5,8%	40,6%	,0%	100,0%
Male	52	16	158	12	64	2	304
	17,1%	5,3%	52,0%	3,9%	21,1%	,7%	100,0%
Total	64	20	216	20	120	2	442
	14,5%	4,5%	48,9%	4,5%	27,1%	,5%	100,0%

$\chi^2 = 22,686$ $P = 0,000$

Table 6: The Distribution of the Participants' Internet Usage Periods as per the Gender Variable

Variables	0-1 hours	2 hours	3 hours	4 hours and above	Total
Female	16	40	32	50	138
	11,6%	29,0%	23,2%	36,2%	100,0%
Male	38	72	58	136	304
	12,5%	23,7%	19,1%	44,7%	100,0%
Total	54	112	90	186	442
	12,2%	25,3%	20,4%	42,1%	100,0%

$\chi^2 = 3,535$ $P = 0,316$

Table 7: The Distribution of the Participants' Internet Usage Periods as per the "Department where they Study Variable"

Variables	0-1 hours	2. hours	3. hours	4. hours and above	Total
Physical Education teacher training	22 18, 6%	30 25, 4%	28 23, 7%	38 32, 2%	118 100, 0%
Coaching education	8 5, 9%	30 22, 1%	16 11, 8%	82 60, 3%	136 100, 0%
Sports management	24 12, 8%	52 27, 7%	46 24, 5%	66 35, 1%	188 100, 0%
Total	54 12, 2%	112 25, 3%	90 20, 4%	186 42, 1%	442 100, 0%

$\chi^2 = 32, 260$ $P = 0, 000$

Table 8: The "Independent Samples, T-Test" Distribution of the Participants' Reasons of Using Social Media as per the "Gender Variable"

Variables	Gender	N	X	t	p
1. For making use of my leisure times	Female	138	1, 5507		
	Male	304	1, 4934		
2. For making new friends	Female	138	2, 5217	6, 252	0, 000*
	Male	304	2, 0263		
3. For communicating with friends	Female	138	1, 4783	, 506	0, 613
	Male	304	1, 5132		
4. For sharing various photographs and videos with my friends	Female	138	1, 6667	3, 023	0, 003*
	Male	304	1, 4605		
5. For having fun and relieving stress	Female	138	1, 5507	, 164	0, 870
	Male	304	1, 5395		
6. For writing comments on the social media contents	Female	138	2, 2029	3, 654	0, 000*
	Male	304	1, 9211		
7. For sending and receiving messages	Female	138	1, 7391	1, 973	0, 049*
	Male	304	1, 5987		
8. For learning about various news and incidents	Female	138	1, 4203	, 093	0, 926
	Male	304	1, 4145		
9. For knowing people better	Female	138	2, 1304	4, 051	0, 000*
	Male	304	1, 8092		
10. For being informed about various issues	Female	138	1, 6812	3, 876	0, 000*
	Male	304	1, 4211		
11. For exchanging opinions with individuals	Female	138	1, 7826	1, 674	0, 095
	Male	304	1, 6579		
12. For shopping	Female	138	1, 8116	, 816	0, 415
	Male	304	1, 7500		

$P < 0, 05^*$

Table 9: "Kruskal Wallis H- Test" Distributions of the Participants Reasons of Using Social Media "as per the "Department where they Study Variable"

Variables	Department	(N) Distribution	(X) Average	(X ²) Value	(P) Value
1. For making use of my leisure times	Physical Education and Sports	118	240,99	5,036	0,081
	Coaching education	136	211,29		
	Sports Management	188	216,65		
	Total	442			
2. For making new friends	Physical Education and Sports	118	258,72	19,234	0,000*
	Coaching education	136	222,65		
	Sports Management	188	197,31		
	Total	442			
3. For communicating with friends	Physical Education and Sports	118	241,50	5,148	0,076
	Coaching education	136	220,76		
	Sports Management	188	209,48		
	Total	442			
4. For sharing various photographs and videos with my friends	Physical Education and Sports	118	254,74	14,259	0,001*
	Coaching education	136	206,19		
	Sports Management	188	211,71		
	Total	442			
5. For having fun and relieving stress	Physical Education and Sports	118	239,69	10,274	0,006*
	Coaching education	136	196,57		
	Sports Management	188	228,12		
	Total	442			
6. For writing comments on the social media contents	Physical Education and Sports	118	257,19	14,417	0,001*
	Coaching education	136	206,26		
	Sports Management	188	210,12		
	Total	442			
7. For sending and receiving messages	Physical Education and Sports	118	242,65	5,644	0,059*
	Coaching education	136	217,93		

	Sports management	188	210, 81		
	Total	442			
8. For learning about various news and incidents	Physical Education and Sports	118	217, 64		
	Coaching education	136	206, 68	5, 580	0, 061
	Sports management	188	234, 65		
	Total	442			
9. For knowing people better	Physical Education and Sports	118	249, 13		
	Coaching education	136	228, 47	13, 257	0, 001*
	Sports management	188	199, 12		
	Total	442			
10. For being informed about various issues	Physical Education and Sports	118	235, 57		
	Coaching education	136	234, 59	8, 832	0, 012*
	Sports management	188	203, 20		
	Total	442			
11. For exchanging opinions with individuals	Physical Education and Sports	118	230, 99		
	Coaching education	136	229, 19	3, 173	0, 205
	Sports management	188	209, 98		
	Total	442			
12. For shopping	Physical Education and Sports	118	233, 65		
	Coaching education	136	220, 91	1, 948	0, 378
	Sports management	188	214, 30		
	Total	442			

P<0, 05*

Table 10: The “Independent Samples, T-Test” Distribution of the Participants’ Opinions regarding Social Media as per the “Gender Variable”

Variables	Gender	N	X	t	p
1. Do you consider social media useful?	Female	138	1, 6812		
	Male	304	1, 5395	2, 198	0, 028*

P<0, 05*

4. Discussion and Results

442 individuals participated in this study conducted to determine the social media usage levels and goals of the students studying in the fields of sports sciences. 68, 8% of them are male and 31, 2% are female. In terms of their age distributions, 37, 1% are at 21-22, 33, 5% are at 23 and above, and 29,4% are at 19-20 years of age. When it comes to the departments they study, 42,5% are in sports management, 30,8% are in coaching education, and 26,7% are in physical education and sports teacher training (Table 1).

The participants' status of having an internet network or not is questioned. According to this query, 69,7% answered yes and %30, 3 answered no to the state of having home internet and 91,4% answered yes and 8, 6% answered no to the state of having the internet in their phones (Table 2). According to these data, we can say that the generality of the participants have the internet network at their homes or on their cell phones.

For the query of the participants' communication tools and programs they use, usage times, and the state of the internet to be sufficient, 89,1% stated that they use a cell phone; regarding the social account packages, 48, 9% stated that they use Instagram, 27,1% stated that they use WhatsApp, and 14, 5% stated that they use Facebook, their daily usage periods are 4 hours and above in %42, 1, 2 hours in %25,3, 3 hours in 20, and 4%, 1 hour in 12, 2%. For the state of the internet package to be sufficient 57% answered yes and 43% answered no (Table 3).

As a result of the data obtained, we can say that the generality of the participants prevalently use cell phones as a communication tool and Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook as social accounts, that they use them for at least 1 hour and 2-4 hours in general, and that their internet packages were mainly sufficient. The findings of (Lenhart, 2013; Lenhart et al, 2010; Dikme, 2013) in their studies for social media usage that the websites like Facebook and Twitter are used among the youth in a widespread manner; of (Subrahmanyam, Reich, Waechter and Espinoza , 2008; Ergenç, 2011) in their studies that social media users visit social media many times during the day; and of (Vural and Bat, 2010) that the period students spend in the social networks is between 1 and 3 hours on average tally with our findings.

When we examine the answers of the students in terms of the query of the participants' use of communication tools according to the gender variable, in general, it appears that 89, 1% give the answer of cell phones. In the comparative statistical analysis for the answers given according to the variable of gender, X^2 value is (4, 540 $p=0, 103, p>0, 05$). This value is not statistically significant (Table 4). According to these data, we can say that the generality of the participants use cell phones as communication tools.

In the comparative statistical analysis of the answers given by the participants for the social account network query they use, according to the gender variable, X^2 value was found as (22, 686 $P= 0, 000, P<0, 05$). This value is statistically significant. Detailed examination of the table shows that the males mainly use Instagram and Facebook

while the females use WhatsApp (Table 5). The finding and opinion of (Koçer, 2012) that in the state of internet and social media usage and having a blog, there are differences among the genders tally with our study finding.

In the comparative statistical analysis of the answers given by the participants for the internet usage periods query, according to the gender variable, X^2 value was found as (3, 535, $P=0,316$ $p>0,05$). This value is not statistically significant. Detailed examination of the table shows that the participants use the internet mainly for 4 hours and above (Table 6). According to these data, we can say that there are no differences between the participants' genders in terms of internet usage periods. The opinions of (Otrar and Argin, 2014) in their study that the students spend a large portion of their times in social media networks and those networks in question have been a part of their lives support the findings in our study.

In the comparative statistical analysis of the answers given by the participants for the internet usage periods query, according to the departments where they study, X^2 value was found as (32, 260 $P=0,000$, $P<0,05$). This value is statistically significant (Table 7). Detailed examination of the table shows that the students studying in the coaching department use the internet and allocate their time more than the other department students.

In Table 8, the participants' reasons for using the social media according to the "gender variable" are being queried. Of these queries:

In the answers given to the question of I am using it for "**Making use of my leisure times**," the statistical analysis value was found as ($t=,868$, $p=0,386$) (Table 8. 1). This value is not significant ($p>0,05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1,5507$) and that of the males is ($X=1,4934$).

In the answers given to the question of I am using it for "**Making new friends**" according to genders, the statistical analysis value was found as ($t=6,252$, $p<0,000$) (Table 8. 2). This value is highly significant ($p<0,05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=2,5217$) higher than that of males ($X=2,0263$). This result shows that the females use social media for making new friends more than males. In the statistical analysis of the answers given to the question of I am using it for "**Communicating with friends**," as per genders, ($t=,506$, $p=0,613$) was found (Table 8. 3). This value is not significant ($P>0,05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1,4783$) and that of the male participants is ($X=1,5132$).

In the answers given by the participants to the question of I am using it for "**Sharing various photographs and videos with my friends**," according to the gender variable, the comparative statistics analysis value was found as ($t=3,023$, $p=0,003$) (Table 8. 4). This value shows that a significant difference is present ($p<0,05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1,6667$) higher than that of males ($X=1,4605$). According to this result, we can say that the female participants use the social media more for sharing various photographs and videos with their friends than males.

In the analysis of the answers given by the participants to the question of I am using it for **“Having fun and relieving stress,”** ($t=, 164, p=0, 870$) was found (Table 8. 5). This value is not statistically significant ($p>0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1, 5507$) and that of the male participants is ($X=1, 5395$).

In the answers given to the question of I am using it for **“Writing comments on the social media contents,”** comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($t=3, 654, p=0, 000$) (Table 8. 6). This value is highly significant ($p<0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=2, 2029$) and that of the male participants is ($X=1, 9211$). According to the data obtained, females use the social media more for writing comments on the social media contents than males.

In the comparative analysis of answers given to the question of I am using it for **“Sending and receiving messages,”** the analysis value was found as ($t=1, 973, p=0, 049$) (Table 8. 7). This value is statistically significant ($p<0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1, 7391$) and that of the male participants is ($X=1, 5987$). According to these results, we can say that females use the social media more for sending and receiving messages than males.

In the comparative statistical analysis of the participants' answers given to the question of I am using it for **“Learning about various news and incidents,”** ($t=, 093, p=0, 926$) was found (Table 8. 8). These values are not statistically significant ($p>0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1, 4203$) and that of the males is ($X=1, 4145$).

In the answers of the participants given to the question of I am using it for **“Knowing people better,”** comparative statistical analysis value is ($t=4, 051, p=0, 000$) (Table 8. 9). This value is highly significant ($p<0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=2, 1304$) and that of the males is ($X=1, 8092$). According to this result, females use the social media more for knowing people better than males.

In the answers of the participants given to the question of I am using it for **“Being informed about various issues,”** the comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($t=3, 876, p=0, 000$) (Table 8. 10). This value is statistically significant a lot ($p<0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1, 6812$) and that of the males is ($X=1, 4211$). As a result of these data, we can say that females use the social media more for being informed about various issues.

In the answers of the participants given to the question of I am using it for **“Exchanging opinions with individuals,”** the comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($t=1, 674, p=0, 095$) (Table 8. 11). These values are not statistically significant ($p>0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1, 7826$) and that of the males is ($X=1, 6579$).

In the answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for **“Shopping,”** comparative analysis value was found as ($t=, 816, p=0, 415$) (Table 8. 12). This value is not statistically significant ($p>0, 05$). The average of the answers given by females to this question is ($X=1, 8116$) and that of the males is ($X=1, 7500$).

In view of the foregoing data, we can say that when we evaluate the participants' objective of use of social media in terms of the averages of the answers they gave, they use social media in general, for making new friends, writing comments on the social media contents, knowing people better, exchanging opinions, messaging, shopping, being informed about various issues, having fun and relieving stress, sharing various photographs, and making use of leisure times in general despite the presence of significant differences according to the genders in the answers in some purposes of usage. The findings of (Pempek, Yermolayeva and Calvert, 2009; Tham, Croy and Mair, 2013; Akçay, 2011; Sönmez, 2013) in their studies regarding the fact that the young ones use the social media for establishing communication, sharing experiences, playing games, developing interpersonal relations, shopping, acquisition and sharing of knowledge, acquisition of social acquaintances, spending spare times, establishing communication with friends and staying away from stress, and receiving information are in parallel with our study findings.

In Table 9, the participants' "reasons for social media usage" according to the "department where they study" variable is being queried. Of these queries:

In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for "**making use of my leisure times**" according to the department where they study, the comparative analysis value was found as ($X^2=5,036$, $p=0,081$) (Table 9. 1). This value is not statistically significant ($p>0,05$). That is to say, there is no significant difference in social media usage according to the departments where the participants study. It appears that the averages of answers given as per departments are Physical Education and sports teacher training, ($X=240,99$), Coaching education ($X=211,29$), and Sports management ($X=216,65$).

In the comparative statistical analysis of answers given to the question of I am using social media for "**Making new friends**," ($X^2=19,234$, $p=0,000$) was found (Table 9. 2). This value is statistically significant a lot ($p<0,05$). It appears that the averages of answers given as per departments are, Physical Education and sports teacher training, ($X=258,72$), Coaching education ($X=222,65$), Sports management ($X=197,31$). According to these data, we can say that, the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students use social media more than the students of the other departments for making new friends, which is followed by the students of the coaching department.

In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for "**Communicating with friends**" according to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=5,148$, $p=0,076$). These values are not statistically significant ($p>0,05$). The averages of the answers given as per the departments were found as Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=241,50$) Coaching education ($X=220,76$), and Sports management ($X=209,48$).

In the comparative statistical analysis of answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for "**Sharing various photographs and videos with my friends**" according to the departments where they study, ($X^2=14,259$, $p=0,001$) was

found (Table 9. 3). This value is statistically significant ($p < 0, 05$). The averages of the answers given as per the departments appear to be the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=254, 74$), Coaching education ($X=206, 19$), and Sports management ($X=211, 71$). According to these results, we can say that, the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students use social media more than the students of the other departments for sharing various photographs and videos with their friends, which is followed by the students of the sports management department.

In the comparative statistical analysis of answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for **“Having fun and relieving stress”** according to the departments, ($X^2=10, 274, p=0, 006$) was found (Table 9. 4). This value is statistically significant ($p < 0, 05$). The averages of the answers given as per the departments appear to be Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=239, 69$), Coaching education ($X=196, 57$), and Sports management ($X=228, 12$). According to these results, we can say that, the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students use social media more than the students of the other departments for having fun and relieving stress, which is followed by the students of the sports management department.

In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for **“Writing comments on the social media contents”** according to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=14, 417, p=0, 001$) (Table 9. 5). These values are statistically significant ($p < 0, 05$). That is to say, there are significant differences in social media usage according to the departments where they study. The averages of the answers given as per the departments appear to be the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=257, 19$), Coaching education ($X=206, 26$), and Sports management ($X=210, 12$). According to these results, we can say that, the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students use social media more than the students of the other departments for writing comments on the social media contents, which is followed by the students of the sports management department.

In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for **“Sending and receiving messages”** According to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=5, 644, p=0, 059$) (Table 9. 6). This value is statistically significant ($p < 0, 05$). The averages of the answers given appear to be the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=242, 65$), Coaching education ($X=217, 93$), and Sports management ($X=210, 81$). According to these values, we can say that, the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students use social media more than the students of the other departments for sending and receiving messages, which is followed by the students of the coaching department.

In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for **“Learning about various news and incidents”** According to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=5, 580, p=0, 061$) (Table 9. 7). These values are not statistically significant ($p > 0, 05$). The averages of the answers given

as per the variables appear to be the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=217, 64$), Coaching education ($X=206, 68$), and Sports management ($X=234, 65$).

In the comparative statistical analysis of answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for **“Knowing people better”** according to the departments where they study ($X^2=13, 257, p=0, 001$) was found (Table 9. 8). This value is statistically significant ($p<0, 05$). That is to say, the participants exhibit significant difference in social media usage according to the departments where they study. It appears that the averages of answers given as per departments are the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=249, 13$), Coaching education ($X=228, 47$), and Sports management ($X=199, 12$). According to this result, we can say that, the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students use social media more than the students of the other departments for knowing people better, which is followed by the students of the coaching education department.

In the answers given to the question of I am using social media for **“Being informed about various issues”** according to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=8, 832, p=0, 012$) (Table 9. 9). This value is statistically significant ($p<0, 05$). That is to say, there are significant differences in social media usage according to the departments where they study. It appears that the averages of answers given to the question are the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=235, 57$), Coaching education ($X=234, 59$), and Sports management ($X=203, 20$). According to these data, we can say that we can say that, the Coaching education department students use social media more than the students of the sports management department for being informed about various issues.

In the answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for **“Exchanging opinions with individuals”** according to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=3, 173, p=0, 205$) (Table 9. 10). These values are not statistically significant ($p>0, 05$). That is to say, there is no significant difference in opinions in the answers given by the participants to this question. It appears that the averages of answers given as per departments are the Physical Education and sports ($X= 230, 99$), Coaching education ($X=229, 19$), and Sports management ($X=209, 98$).

In the answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for **“Shopping”** according to the department where they study, comparative statistical analysis value was found as ($X^2=1, 948, p=0, 378$) (Table 9. 11). This value is not statistically significant ($p>0, 05$). In the answers of the participants given according to the departments where they study, no significant difference of opinion is present. It appears that the averages of answers given as per departments are the Physical Education and sports teacher training ($X=233, 65$), Coaching education ($X=220, 91$), and Sports management ($X=214, 30$).

When we analyze the answers given by the participants according to the departments where they study in terms of their objectives of social media usage as a result of the foregoing data obtained, we can say that the usage objectives are mainly

same; but, when it comes to the answer averages, the usage objectives of the Physical Education and sports teacher training department students are higher than the students of other departments and those of the coaching department is higher than the sports management department students.

In the comparative statistical analysis of answers of the participants given to the question of I am using social media for *“Do you consider social media useful?”* according to the gender variable, ($t=2, 198, p=0, 028$) was found (Table 10. 1). This value is statistically significant ($p<0, 05$). In the averages of the answers given according to the gender variable, females are ($X=1, 6812$) and males are ($X=1, 5395$) (Table 10). According to these values, we can say that the generality of the participants consider social media useful but the females find it more useful than the males. The opinion of (Aslanyürek et al, 2015) in their study, that in terms of gender, the opinion of female students regarding social media is in a more positive approach than that of the male students tallies with our study finding.

As a result of the data acquired within the scope of the study, we can say that the generality of the participants taking part in the study have internet connections at their homes (89,1%) and in their cell phones (91,4%) and social account networks, that their social accounts are Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook, that the participants use their internet packages between 2 and 4 hours a day, and that their internet package is sufficient in general.

We can say that no significant difference appeared in the internet usage period among genders, that a significant difference took place in the variable of the department where they study, and that the students of the coaching department use the internet more than the students of the other departments.

We can say that no significant difference was observed in their state of using a communication tool according to the gender variable, that they use cell phones in general, there became a significant difference in terms of the social account networks among genders, that the male participants use Instagram and Facebook while the female ones use WhatsApp.

We can say that the participants' purposes of using social media in general are making new friends, writing comments on the social media contents, knowing people better, exchanging opinions, messaging, shopping, being informed about various issues, having fun and relieving stress, sharing various photographs, and making use of their spare times.

We can say that the participants' purposes of using social media as per the departments where they study are mainly same but, when it comes to the answer averages, the students of the Physical Education and sports teacher training department have higher usage purpose ratios than the students of the other departments and students of the coaching department have higher usage purpose ratios than the students of the de sports management department.

We can say that the participants consider social media useful in general but the females find it more useful than males.

Suggestions

- Awareness must be raised among individuals regarding computer and internet usage without detaching from social life for their lives not to be affected negatively.
- Individuals must use the social media for the purposes that will provide benefits to them.
- Educational institutions must convert social media, which is excessively utilized among individuals, into an educational opportunity by means of ensuring its efficient use in education.
- It must be ensured that the lecturers use the social media networks as an educational tool in an efficient manner in their educational processes.
- Individuals must be informed about secure internet and social media usage.

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